

1 Supplemental: Transcriptomic
2 responses of sponge holobionts to in
3 situ, seasonal anoxia and hypoxia

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8 **Supplemental Table 1.** Collection metadata for all sponge samples used in this study.
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Species	Individual	Depth (m)	Oxygen concentration (mg L ⁻¹)	Oxygen condition	Temperature (°C)	Season	Year	Month	Day
<i>Eurypon sp. 2</i>	DC33	19	9.51	Normoxic	15.64	Summer	2018	8	8
<i>Eurypon sp. 2</i>	DC39	14.8	9.51	Normoxic	15	Summer	2018	8	8
<i>Eurypon sp. 2</i>	DC85	24	11.81	Normoxic	11.37	Spring	2019	4	9
<i>Eurypon sp. 2</i>	DC93	27	12.20	Normoxic	12.69	Spring	2019	4	10
<i>Eurypon sp. 2</i>	DC97	27	11.70	Normoxic	11.55	Spring	2019	4	11
<i>Eurypon sp. 2</i>	DC135	20	9.25	Normoxic	14.73	Summer	2019	7	26
<i>Eurypon sp. 2</i>	DC136	20	9.25	Normoxic	14.73	Summer	2019	7	26
<i>Eurypon sp. 2</i>	DC108	27	2.36	Hypoxic	13.04	Summer	2019	7	23
<i>Eurypon sp. 2</i>	DC112	27	1.70	Hypoxic	13.62	Summer	2019	7	24
<i>Eurypon sp. 2</i>	DC114	27	1.70	Hypoxic	13.62	Summer	2019	7	24
<i>Eurypon sp. 2</i>	DC118	27	1.70	Hypoxic	13.62	Summer	2019	7	24
<i>Eurypon sp. 2</i>	DC123	27	1.71	Hypoxic	13.80	Summer	2019	7	25
<i>Eurypon sp. 2</i>	DC131	27	1.37	Hypoxic	13.68	Summer	2019	7	26
<i>Eurypon sp. 2</i>	DC110	27	2.36	Hypoxic	13.04	Summer	2019	7	23
<i>Eurypon sp. 2</i>	DC24	27	0.00	Anoxic	10.80	Summer	2018	8	7
<i>Eurypon sp. 2</i>	DC56	27	0.00	Anoxic	11.88	Summer	2018	8	9
<i>H. stellifera</i>	DC129	20	9.11	Normoxic	14.72	Summer	2019	7	25
<i>H. stellifera</i>	DC105	26.3	2.36	Hypoxic	13.04	Summer	2019	7	23
<i>H. stellifera</i>	DC107	29	2.36	Hypoxic	13.04	Summer	2019	7	23
<i>H. stellifera</i>	DC133	27	1.37	Hypoxic	13.68	Summer	2019	7	26
<i>H. stellifera</i>	DC121	27	1.71	Hypoxic	13.80	Summer	2019	7	25
<i>H. stellifera</i>	DC116	27	1.70	Hypoxic	13.62	Summer	2019	7	24
<i>H. stellifera</i>	DC54	27	0.00	Anoxic	11.88	Summer	2018	9	8
<i>H. stellifera</i>	DC55	27	0.00	Anoxic	11.88	Summer	2018	9	8

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Supplemental Table 2. Table summarizing all stats for reference transcriptomes and metagenomes.

Sequence type	<i>Eurypon</i> sp. 2 holobiont				<i>H. stellifera</i> holobiont			
	mRNA	Total RNA	DNA		mRNA	Total RNA	DNA	
N raw reads (x 10 ⁶)	1,120	1,420	152		793	788	99.8	
N qual filtered: PE, SE (x 10 ⁶)	55.2, 8.29	NA	NA		19.7, 3.10	NA	NA	
N contigs holobiont	147,136	NA	232,756		128,943	NA	88,622	
Target reference (bin) only:	Sponge	Mito-chondria	Thaum-archaeota	Gamma-proteo-bacteria	Sponge	Mito-chondria	Thaum-archaeota	Gamma-proteo-bacteria
N contigs target	127,979	14	370	983	110,497	14	157	546
Mean GC content target	51.0	28.8	58.6	58.2	49.2	25.5	33.2	57.2
N genes	49,911	14	1,556	2,751	62,494	14	1,551	3,057
Mean contig length (bp)	1,047	NA	4,966	6,649	1,135	NA	12,232	12,473
N50 (bp)	1,283	NA	11,143	14,923	1,545	NA	17,952	28,974
% Annotated	39.7	100	69.2	81.5	37.0	100	67.7	84.8
<i>BUSCOs</i> :	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
N complete (%)	94.7	NA	90.0	95.2	95.9	NA	97.0	96.5
N partial (%)	96.8	NA	92.8	96.7	96.9	NA	97.7	97.0
N missing (%)	3.17	NA	7.20	3.23	3.07	NA	2.35	3.01

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Supplemental Table 3. Nitrite concentrations with depth in Lough Hyne, sampled on 26/7/2019 when conditions at the sponge sampling depth were hypoxic. Anoxia occurred at a depth of 33 m.

Depth (m)	1	5	10	15	20	25	27	30	32	34	35	36	38
Nitrite concentration (µM)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.31	0.81	0.76	1.11

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 21 **Supplemental Figure 1.** Significantly enriched GO categories of biological processes in A.
 22 *Eurypon* sp. 2 (34 GO terms) and B. *Hymerphia stellifera* (18 GO terms) in normoxia vs. hypoxia.
 23 Red GO terms are significantly upregulated in hypoxia, and blue terms are downregulated. The
 24 font and text size correspond to the p values (see legend) of Fisher's exact tests of GO category
 25 enrichment. The numbers in front of the GO categories correspond to the number of
 26 significantly differentially expressed genes (numerator) based on treatment out of the total
 27 number of genes in the dataset belonging to that GO category (denominator). GO categories
 28 are clustered hierarchically based on shared genes between the categories, meaning that those
 29 on the same branch are subsets of one another.
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 32 **Supplemental Figure 2.** Significantly enriched GO categories of biological processes in A.
 33 *Eurypon* sp. 2 (12 GO terms) and B. *Hymerphia stellifera* (17 GO terms) in normoxia vs. anoxia.
 34 Orange GO terms are significantly upregulated in anoxia, and black terms are downregulated.
 35 The font and text size correspond to the p values (see legend) of Fisher's exact tests of GO
 36 category enrichment. The numbers in front of the GO categories correspond to the number of
 37 significantly differentially expressed genes (numerator) based on treatment out of the total
 38 number of genes in the dataset belonging to that GO category (denominator). GO categories
 39 are clustered hierarchically based on shared genes between the categories, meaning that those
 40 on the same branch are subsets of one another.

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 44 **Supplemental Figure 3.** Significantly enriched GO categories of biological processes in A.
 45 *Eurypon* sp. 2 (12 GO terms) and B. *Hymerphia stellifera* (17 GO terms) in hypoxia vs. anoxia.
 46 Pink GO terms are significantly upregulated in anoxia, and cyan terms are downregulated. The
 47 font and text size correspond to the p values (see legend) of Fisher's exact tests of GO category
 48 enrichment. The numbers in front of the GO categories correspond to the number of
 49 significantly differentially expressed genes (numerator) based on treatment out of the total
 50 number of genes in the dataset belonging to that GO category (denominator). GO categories
 51 are clustered hierarchically based on shared genes between the categories, meaning that those
 52 on the same branch are subsets of one another.
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 55 **Supplemental Figure 4.** All significantly differentially expressed genes within the KOG class
 56 'replication, recombination and repair' (RRR) in both sponge species. For *Eurypon* sp. 2 the
 57 three pairwise comparisons are shown in A (normoxia vs. hypoxia), B (hypoxia vs. normoxia),
 58 and C (anoxia vs. hypoxia). Significantly differentially expressed RRR genes in *H. stellifera* are
 59 shown in D and E for normoxia vs. hypoxia and hypoxia vs. anoxia, respectively. Samples
 60 collected under normoxia, hypoxia and anoxia are shown in blue, orange and red, respectively.
 61 Heatmaps are scaled based on row (gene) mean, i.e. Z-scores.
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 64 **Supplemental Figure 5.** All significantly differentially expressed genes within the KOG class
 65 'energy production and conversion' (EPC) in both sponge species. For *Eurypon* sp. 2 the three
 66 pairwise comparisons are shown in A (normoxia vs. hypoxia), B (hypoxia vs. normoxia), and C
 67 (anoxia vs. hypoxia). Significantly differentially expressed EPC genes in *H. stellifera* are shown in
 68 D-F for normoxia vs. hypoxia, normoxia vs. anoxia, and hypoxia vs. normoxia, respectively.
 69 Samples collected under normoxia, hypoxia and anoxia are shown in blue, orange and red,
 70 respectively. Heatmaps are scaled based on row (gene) mean, i.e. Z-scores.

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A. *Eurypon* sp. 2

B. *Hymeraphia stellifera*

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Supplemental Figure 6. Mitochondrial gene expression under different oxygen conditions in A. *Eurypon* sp. 2 and B. *Hymeraphia stellifera*. Color code corresponds to Schuster, Strehlow et. al. 2021. Asterisk (*) indicates a significant difference in the *nad2* gene of *Eurypon* sp. 2.

80 **Supplemental Figure 7.** Gene expression profiles of sponge associated microbes under varied
 81 oxygen concentrations compared to each other. A. Clustered heatmap (based on correlation) of
 82 COG class (rows) enrichments for upregulated or downregulated genes for *Thaumarchaeota*
 83 symbionts. B. Clustered heatmap of COG class enrichments in *Gammaproteobacteria*
 84 symbionts. Highlighted text colors correspond to the sponge species to which each symbiont is
 85 associated. (Purple: *Hymenochirus stellifera* [Hs], Cyan: *Eurypon* sp. 2 [Es]). Up or down
 86 regulation with respect to normoxia is indicated in 'Hypox' (hypoxia) and 'Anox' (anoxia)
 87 columns, and differential regulation with respect to hypoxia is shown in 'Hypox vs. Anox'
 88 columns, i.e. upregulated COGs (red delta ranks) are upregulated in anoxia with respect to
 89 hypoxia. Within each column on the heatmap, COGs that are significantly enriched (FDR-
 90 adjusted $p < 0.05$) are outlined in black boxes.
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93 **Supplemental Figure 8.** Significantly differentially expressed heat shock protein (HSP) genes
 94 in sponges in response to deoxygenation. A. *Eurypon* sp. 2. B. *H. stellifera*. Asterisks: *, ** and
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96 *** indicate significant differences in expression level between normoxia vs. hypoxia, normoxia
97 vs. anoxia, and anoxia vs. hypoxia, respectively.
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119 **Supplemental Figure 9.** Maximum Likelihood (ML) phylogeny based on nitroreductase
120 protein alignment. Numbers on branches indicate bootstrap support (BS) values. The
121 position of the nitroreductase proteins from *Hymenaphia stellifera* (hs) are highlighted in
122 red and of *Eurypon* sp. 2 (es) in pink. Sequences from Kraft et al. [\(2022\)](#) are
123 highlighted in blue.
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